

Installation Guide for ERP Software System YEROTH-ERP-3.0

PROF. DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. XAVIER NOUNDOU

VERSION: November 7, 2023

Contents

Contents	3
List of Figures	5
List of Tables	7
1 INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 Typography	9
1.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS	9
1.2.1 SCREEN (computer Desktop)	9
1.2.2 RANDOM ACCESS MEMORY (RAM)	9
1.3 Prerequisite Software	9
1.4 Files Required for Installation Procedure	10
2 AUTOMATED INSTALLATION with gdebi-gtk OR gdebi	11
2.1 Installation of gdebi-gtk and gdebi	11
2.2 Installation with gdebi-gtk	11
2.3 Installation with gdebi	12
3 MANUAL Installation Procedure Of YEROTH–ERP–3.0 – DBMS	13
3.1 INSTALLATION STEPS OF mariadb-server (ON REMOTE COMPUTER–SERVER)	13
3.2 Installation of mariadb-server (ON REMOTE COMPUTER–SERVER)	13
3.3 Modify MYSQL CONFIGURATION FILE '/etc/mysql/mariadb.conf.d/50-server.cnf'	13
4 MANUAL Installation Procedure Of YEROTH–ERP–3.0	15
4.1 INSTALLATION STEPS OF YEROTH–ERP–3.0	15
4.2 Installation of gdebi and expect	15
4.3 Installation of Qt, Texlive, and of YEROTH–ERP–3.0	16
4.4 Sample 2 computers store	17
4.5 Sample decentralized multi sites supermarket	17
4.6 Modify (IF REQUIRED) CONFIGURATION FILE 'yeroth-erp-3-0.properties' to access YEROTH–ERP–3.0 – DBMS	18
Appendix	19
A Standard Administrative User Account 'admin'	19
B HOW TO CONFIGURE A POINT–OF–SALE THERMAL PRINTER	21
C PREFERENCE FILES FOR A USER OF YEROTH–ERP–3.0	23

D	YEROTH-ERP-3.0 CONFIGURATION FILES	25
E	how to uninstall 'YEROTH-ERP-3.0'	27
F	how to uninstall 'YEROTH-ERP-3.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON'	29

List of Figures

2.1	Gdebi-gtk user graphical interface.	11
4.1	Sample 2 computers store.	17
4.2	Sample decentralized multi sites supermarket.	17

List of Tables

1.1	Prerequisite software for installation of YEROTH-ERP-3.0.	9
1.2	Files required for installation of YEROTH-ERP-3.0.	10

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Typography

Within this guide, all commands written in the following type setting:

`command`

are to be executed as "super user" ("root user").

1.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

1.2.1 SCREEN (computer Desktop)

YEROTH-ERP-3.0 is best screen sized on a screen of 22 inch and higher !

1.2.2 RANDOM ACCESS MEMORY (RAM)

YEROTH-ERP-3.0 could be used with a computer with a Random Access Memory (RAM) of about 512 Mb.

HOWEVER, FOR MAXIMUM PERFORMANCE, I RECOMMEND AT LEAST 2 GB OF RAM MEMORY !

1.3 Prerequisite Software

Table 1.1: Prerequisite software for installation of [YEROTH-ERP-3.0](#).

Software	Versions
Debian	11.1 (bullseye)
gdebi	0.9.5.7 + nmu5
mariadb-server	10.5.12 - 0 + deb11u1
mariadb-client	10.5.12 - 0 + deb11u1
Qt	5.15.2
Texlive	2020.20210202 - 3

1.4 Files Required for Installation Procedure

Table 1.2: Files required for installation of YEROTH-ERP-3.0.

Files
"yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb"
"yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb"
"yeroth-erp-3-0-system-daemon.deb"

Table 1.2 illustrates files required for installing YEROTH-ERP-3.0.

Chapter 2

AUTOMATED INSTALLATION with gdebi-gtk OR gdebi

Figure 2.1: Gdebi-gtk user graphical interface.

2.1 Installation of gdebi-gtk and gdebi

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
apt -y install gdebi-gtk gdebi
```

2.2 Installation with gdebi-gtk

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
gdebi-gtk yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb
```

3. press button "Install Package"
4. repeat the previous command with files "**yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb**" and "**yeroth-erp-3-0-system-daemon.deb**" respectively.

2.3 Installation with gdebi

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
gdebi -n yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb
```

3. repeat the previous command with files "**yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb**" and "**yeroth-erp-3-0-system-daemon.deb**" respectively.

Chapter 3

MANUAL Installation Procedure Of YEROTH-ERP-3.0 – DBMS

3.1 INSTALLATION STEPS OF mariadb-server (ON REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER)

Following steps have to be followed in order to have a well functioning installation of YEROTH-ERP-3.0 – DBMS:

1. install database software mariadb-server (ON REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER)
2. modify IF REQUIRED MYSQL CONFIGURATION FILE '/etc/mysql/mariadb.conf.d/50-server.cnf' (ON REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER).

3.2 Installation of mariadb-server (ON REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER)

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
apt -y install mariadb-server mariadb-client
```

3.3 Modify MYSQL CONFIGURATION FILE '/etc/mysql/mariadb.conf.d/50-server.cnf'

APPLY THE FOLLOWING INSTRUCTIONS ONLY IF YOU REQUIRE YOUR YEROTH-ERP-3.0 – DBMS to be on a REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER DIFFERENT FROM 'localhost'!

1. MODIFY INLINE 'bind-address = 127.0.0.1' TO 'bind-address =YE.YF.YG.YH' WHERE 'YE.YF.YG.YH' REPRESENTS PUBLIC IP ADDRESS OF LOCAL DBMS-COMPUTER
2. this step requires a reboot of DBMS-mariadb-server:

```
service mariadb restart
```


Chapter 4

MANUAL Installation Procedure Of YEROTH-ERP-3.0

4.1 INSTALLATION STEPS OF YEROTH-ERP-3.0

Following steps have to be followed in order to have a well functioning installation of YEROTH-ERP-3.0:

1. install gdebi and expect software
2. install YEROTH-ERP-3.0 (Qt and Texlive are automatically installed)
3. modify configuration file 'yeroth-erp-3-0.properties' to access YEROTH-ERP-3.0 – DBMS.

4.2 Installation of gdebi and expect

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
apt -y install gdebi expect
```

4.3 Installation of Qt, Texlive, and of YEROTH-ERP-3.0

1. Open a "bash-terminal"

2. type command:

```
gdebi -n yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb
```

3. then type command (INSTALLS ALERT AND SAVE-BACKUP SYSTEM daemon):

```
gdebi -n yeroth-erp-3-0-system-daemon.deb
```

4. then finally type command:

```
gdebi -n yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb
```

This command automatically installs Qt, and Texlive.

4.4 Sample 2 computers store

Figure 4.1: Sample 2 computers store.

4.5 Sample decentralized multi sites supermarket

Figure 4.2: Sample decentralized multi sites supermarket.

4.6 **Modify (IF REQUIRED) CONFIGURATION FILE 'yeroth-erp-3-0.properties' to access YEROTH-ERP-3.0 – DBMS**

APPLY THE FOLLOWING INSTRUCTIONS ONLY IF YOU REQUIRE YOUR YEROTH-ERP-3.0 – DBMS to be on a REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER DIFFERENT FROM 'localhost'!

1. FILE 'YEROTH-ERP-3-0.PROPERTIES' IS LOCATED AT LOCAL DRIVE:
'/opt/yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-configurations-data'
2. MODIFY INLINE 'db_ip_address=localhost' TO 'db_ip_address=YE.YF.YG.YH' WHERE 'YE.YF.YG.YH' REPRESENTS REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER-DBMS IP ADDRESS.

Appendix A

Standard Administrative User Account 'admin'

After [YEROTH-ERP-3.0](#) successful installation, the application is accessible using a standard administrative user account with the following credentials:

1. user name: **admin**
2. user password: **admin1**

This administrative user account could be modified at your wish.

Appendix B

HOW TO CONFIGURE A POINT-OF-SALE THERMAL PRINTER

Appendix C

PREFERENCE FILES FOR A USER OF YEROTH-ERP-3.0

Appendix D

YEROTH-ERP-3.0 CONFIGURATION FILES

Appendix E

how to uninstall 'YEROTH-ERP-3.0'

1. Open a "bash-terminal"

2. type command:

```
apt -y --purge remove yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-english
```

3. FINALLY, type command:

```
apt -y --purge remove yeroth-erp-3-0-standalone-configurations-data-english
```


Appendix F

how to uninstall 'YEROTH-ERP-3.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON'

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type command:

```
apt -y --purge remove yeroth-erp-3-0-system-daemon
```